

Avifauna and their feeding guilds in Cheethwari and adjoining villages of Northern Jaipur, Rajasthan, India

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Abstract

A random survey documenting the avifauna was conducted from December 2018 to December 2020 in agricultural–rural areas in Cheethwari villages and adjoining areas from Jaipur district, Rajasthan, India. During the survey, ninety-six species belonging to 48 families under 16 orders were recorded viz., Accipitriformes (3 species), Anseriformes (1), Apodiformes (1), Bucerotiformes (2), Charadriiformes (7), Columbiformes (5), Coraciiformes (4), Cuculiformes (3), Galliformes (5), Gruiformes (3), Passeriformes (49), Pelecaniformes (4), Piciformes (3), Podicipediformes (1), Psittaciformes (2), Strigiformes (2). Among these, the family Muscicapidae (6), Columbidae (5), Phasianidae (5), Cisticolidae (5), and Sturnidae families were dominantly represented by more species, whereas 25 families were found to be represented by single bird species. Based on the feeding guild, it is apparent that the avifauna of this region is dominated by omnivorous (41 species), followed by insectivorous, carnivorous, granivorous, frugivorous, insectivorous, granivorous, frugivorous & granivorous, and insectivorous birds. Twelve winter visitors, including the iconic migrant Rosy Starling, *Pastor roseus* (Linnaeus, 1758), and two summer visitors, were recorded during the present observations. Shikra, Short-toed Snake Eagle, Indian Peafowl, and Rufous-fronted Prinia are listed under Schedule- I of the WPA, and the remaining are listed under Schedule II of the WPA.

Keywords: Jaipur, Feeding, birds, Agriculture, WPA

Introduction

Birds in India are known to be affected by factors including land-use change, urbanization, ecosystem degradation, monocultures, disease, infrastructure development, pet trade, hunting, pollution, and climate change (SoIB, 2023). Jaipur, popularly known as the Pink City, is the capital of the northwestern state of Rajasthan in India. Rajasthan is India's largest state, covering 10.4 percent of the

country's total land area, and has a rich and varied flora and fauna. Jaipur has an average yearly temperature of 24.6°C, average annual precipitation of 528 mm, and humidity of 48% with tropical dry and deciduous forest types. In the Indian subcontinent, 1371 bird species have been documented (eBird, 2024), out of which 489 (35.7%) bird species have been reported from Rajasthan (eBird, 2024) and 361 species (eBird, 2024) from Jaipur. In eastern Jaipur, Moundiotiya (2005) reported 100 bird species belonging to 38 families, mostly spotted during the winter season at Jamwa Ramgarh Lake. Meanwhile, Bhardwaj (2018) reported 218 species from Jamwa Ramgarh Wildlife Sanctuary. Moundiotiya *et al.* (2005) reported 180 bird species in two water bodies, Jal Mahal Lake (urban) and Kalakho Lake (rural) from Jaipur. For the first time, avian diversity was observed in Cheethwari village, 10 km from sub-district Chomu and 40km from district headquarters Jaipur. The present study aimed to investigate bird diversity, feeding guild, and conservation status in agricultural-rural areas, as no previous documentation work has been undertaken in Cheethwari and adjoining villages.

Material and methods

Study Area

The current study was carried out on the feeding guilds and avian diversity in Cheethwari village (27°08'20.7"N 75°48'08.8"E) and the nearby villages, viz. The following locations are under the Chomu tehsil of the Jaipur district, Rajasthan, India: Samode (27°09'02.3"N 75°48'54.5"E), Moriija (27°09'35.5"N 75°45'26.0"E), Bilonchi (27°08'42.8"N 75°52'31.3"E), Fatehpura Bansa-khala (27°09' N 55.7" 75°49' 56.4" E), Kushalpura Basa (27°11'14.0"N 75°48'34.4"E), and Mahar Kalan (27°13'14.6"N 75°49'54.8"E). The Aravalli hill range runs through the region, which is among the four physiographic regions of the state (Rajasthan Foundation, 2024). Agriculture is prevalent in the majority of the study area. The study area comprises mostly agricultural habitats, with a few forest patches and a water body. Crops are cultivated across different seasons; Rabi crops are Fenugreek, Taramira, Mustard, Rapeseed, Peas, and Wheat. Pearl millet, Sorghum, Green Gram, Cowpea, Sesamum, Groundnut, and Cluster-bean are Kharif crops. The typical forest vegetation patches contain the following trees: viz. *Acacia nilotica* (kikar), *Prosopis juliflora* (vilayati babul), *Prosopis cineraria* (khejri), *Ziziphus mauritiana* (ber), *Dalbergia sissoo* (shisham), *Azadirachta indica* (neem), *Ficus religiosa* (peepal), *Saccharum munja* (munja), *Calotropis procera* (aak), *Morus alba* (mulberry), *Leptadenia pyrotechnica* (khip), and *Euphorbia caducifolia* (danda thor).

Figure 1. Cheetwari and adjoining areas of Jaipur in Rajasthan (Courtesy: Google Earth)

The random visits and surveys were conducted in different sites from December 2018 to December 2020 to document avifauna. The surveys were conducted during the early hours of the day, 7.00 to 11.00 AM, and 3.00 to 5.30 PM. During the observations, the bird species were recorded through direct observation, using a 10x42 pair of binoculars and cameras (Canon EOS1200D EFS 55-250 MM and Canon EOS 80 D Canon lens EF 400MM 1:5.6) for taking photographs. Identification of birds, feeding guild and their migratory status was done using Grimett *et al.* (1999). The conservation status was assigned as per the updated International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) and Wildlife Protection Act (WPA) (Indian Birds, 2024).

Results and Discussion

During the survey, a total of 96 bird species were reported belonging to 16 orders (Accipitriformes, Anseriformes, Apodiformes, Bucerotiformes, Charadriiformes, Columbiformes, Coraciiformes, Cuculiformes, Galliformes, Gruiformes, Passeriformes, Pelecaniformes, Piciformes, Podicipediformes, Psittaciformes, Strigiformes) and 47 families (Accipitridae, Aegithinidae, Alaudidae, Alcedinidae, Anatidae, Apodidae, Ardeidae, Bucerotidae, Campephagidae, Charadriidae,

Cisticolidae, Columbidae, Coraciidae, Corvidae, Cuculidae, Dicruridae, Emberizidae, Estrildidae, Hirundinidae, Laniidae, Leiotrichidae, Megalaimidae, Meropidae, Motacillidae, Muscicapidae, Nectariniidae, Oriolidae, Paradoxornithidae, Paridae, Passeridae, Phasianidae, Phylloscopidae, Picidae, Ploceidae, Podicipedidae, Psittacidae, Pycnonotidae, Rallidae, Recurvirostridae, Rhipiduridae, Scolopacidae, Stenostiridae, Strigidae, Sturnidae, Sylviidae, Turnicidae, Upupidae, and Vangidae).

Of the total 16 orders, order Passeriformes represents 52 % (50 species) (Figure 1) and among the 47 families Muscicapidae with 6.3 % representation is the most represented (Figure 2). Indian Robin, Indian scops Owl, Bank myna, Brahminy starling are endemic to India. Out of 96 bird species, 18 are directly related with water bodies, namely White-throated Kingfisher, Knob-billed Duck, Great egret, Cattle Egret, Indian Pond heron, Yellow-wattled Lapwing, Red-wattled Lapwing, White Wagtail, Yellow Wagtail, White-browed Wagtail, Little Grebe, Common Moorhen, Eurasian Coot, White-breasted Waterhen, Black-winged Stilt, Wood Sandpiper, Green Sandpiper, and Common Sandpiper. Regarding conservation status, all the species are listed under the Least Concern (LC) category of IUCN. The Wildlife (Protection) Act of 1972 includes six schedules providing varying degrees of protection to fauna occurring in India. Schedule I and Schedule II get absolute protection; offenses under these schedules attract maximum penalties. Shikra, Short-toed Snake Eagle, Indian Peafowl, Rufous-fronted Prinia, Yellow-crowned woodpecker, and Indian Scops Owl are listed under Schedule I of WPA, all the other bird species are listed under Schedule II. At the same time, the Rock Pigeon and House Crow are not protected. During the study, observations of sociocultural and religious feeding of birds was observed at the Shri Bhomiya Ji Maharaj Mandir on a hilltop in the Cheetwari village.

Figure 1. Order-wise distribution of species observed

A total of 244 species of birds belonging to 136 genera under 18 orders and 53 families have been reported as significant components of the fauna of the agroecosystem of India, characterized by the dominance of only a few granivorous and omnivorous species (Dhindsa & Saini, 1994). However the present study based on field observations and available literature recorded the following: Omnivorous species (42) followed by Insectivorous (24), Carnivorous (18), Granivorous (04), Frugivorous (01), Insectivorous & Granivorous (03), Frugivorous & Granivorous (02), Frugivorous & Insectivorous (01), Nectivorous (01) (Fig. 2). It is evident from this information that there seems to be a dietary overlap of coexisting species, which warrants further study along with seasonal changes in diet diversity. A similar trend was observed in an avian diversity study undertaken in the neighboring Jhunjhunu district, 41.58% of birds were insectivorous, followed by omnivorous (26.73%), carnivorous (15.84%), frugivorous (2.97%), granivorous (11.88%), and nectarivorous (0.99%) (Shekhawat & Bhatnagar, 2014).

Figure 2. Feeding guild of the avifauna observed

In terms of their migratory status, twelve winter visitors, including the iconic migrant Rosy starling, *Pastor roseus* (Linnaeus, 1758), two summer visitors were recorded, while two residents known to exhibit local migration and one resident exhibiting winter migration were recorded (Table 1). The Spotted Owlet, Rose Ringed Parakeet, Common Moorhen, and Red-wattled Lapwing were found to be breeding in this region. Two brood parasites, the Asian Koel (*Eudynamys scolopaceus*) and Indian Cuckoo (*Cuculus micropterus*) (Gould, 1838; Praveen & Lowther, 2020) were reported during the observation. The Asian Koel is widespread with hosts *viz.*, Black Drongo *Dicrurus macrocercus*, Long-tailed Shrike *Lanius schach*, House Crow *Corvus splendens*, Large-billed Crow *Corvus macrorhynchos*, Red-vented Bulbul *Pycnonotus cafer*, Common Myna *Acridotheres tristis*. While the common Cuckoo with a range covering much of the Oriental Region is known to parasitize Black-hooded Oriole *Oriolus xanthornus*, Streaked Spiderhunter *Arachnothera magna* and Black Drongo *Dicrurus macrocercus*. During the present observations, Black Drongo *Dicrurus macrocercus*, Long-tailed Shrike *Lanius schach*, House Crow *Corvus splendens*, Red-vented Bulbul *Pycnonotus cafer*, Common Myna *Acridotheres tristis* were observed warranting future studies on brood parasitism in the study area.

Conclusion

The present study is the first report on the avian diversity in Cheetwari and surrounding areas of Rural Jaipur. The diverse feeding guilds of the birds documented, their trophic interaction, and their impacts on agriculture, including pest control, crop damage, etc., needs to be quantified for biodiversity documentation and agriculture production. A detailed study of the breeding ecology of the avian fauna of the region needs to be undertaken to establish the instances above of co-occurrence of brood parasites and host bird species. The agrarian ecosystems and the cultural aspects of the local community and vital ecosystem services like regulation (Ex, biocontrol of crop pests) and cultural services (Ex, providing anthropogenic food to wild birds like peafowls) need to be assessed.

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Appendices

Table 1. Check-list of avifauna with their feeding guilds and migratory status

Sl. No.	Family	Common Name	Scientific Name	Migratory status	Feeding Guild
1.ORDER – ACCIPITRIFORMES					
1.	Accipitridae	Shikra	<i>Accipiter badius</i> (Gmelin, 1788)	R	C
2.		Short-toed Snake Eagle	<i>Circaetus gallicus</i> (Gmelin, 1788)	R	C
3.		Black-Winged Kite	<i>Elanus caeruleus</i> (Desfontaines, 1789)	R	C
2.ORDER – ANSERIFORMES					
4.	Anatidae	Knob-billed Duck	<i>Sarkidiornis melanotos</i> (Pennant, 1769)	R/ LM	O
3.ORDER – APODIFORMES					
5.	Apodidae	Little Swift	<i>Apus affinis</i> (Gray, 1830)	R	I
4.ORDER – BUCEROTIFORMES					
6.	Upupidae	Eurasian Hoopoe	<i>Upupa epops</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	R / LM	O
7.	Bucerotidae	Indian Grey Hornbill	<i>Ocyrceros birostris</i> (Scopoli, 1786)	R	O
5.ORDER – CHARADRIIFORMES					
8.	Charadriidae	Yellow Wattled Lapwing	<i>Vanellus malabaricus</i> (Boddaert, 1783)	R	C
9.		Red-wattled Lapwing	<i>Vanellus indicus</i> (Boddaert, 1783)	R	C
10.	Recurvirostridae	Black-winged Stilt	<i>Himantopus himantopus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	R / WV	C
11.	Scolopacidae	Wood Sandpiper	<i>Tringa glareola</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	WV	C
12.		Common Sandpiper	<i>Actitis hypoleucos</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	WV	C
13.		Green Sandpiper	<i>Tringa ochropus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	WV	C
14.	Turnicidae	Barred Buttonquail	<i>Turnix suscitator</i> (Gmelin, 1789)	R	O
6.ORDER – COLUMBIFORMES					
15.	Columbidae	Laughing Dove	<i>Spilopelia senegalensis</i> (Linnaeus, 1766)	R	G
16.		Red Collared Dove	<i>Streptopelia tranquebarica</i> (Hermann, 1804)	R	G
17.		Eurasian Collared Dove	<i>Streptopelia decaocto</i> (Frivaldszky, 1838)	R	G
18.		Yellow Footed Green Pigeon	<i>Treron phoenicopterus</i> (Latham, 1790)	R	F
19.		Rock Pigeon	<i>Columba livia</i> (Gmelin, 1789)	R	G
7. ORDER – CORACIIFORMES					
20.	Alcedinidae	White-throated Kingfisher	<i>Halcyon smyrnensis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	R	C
21.	Coraciidae	Indian Roller	<i>Coracias benghalensis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	R	C
22.	Meropidae	Blue-cheeked Bee-eater	<i>Merops persicus</i> (Pallas, 1773)	SV	I
23.		Asian Green Bee-eater	<i>Merops orientalis</i> (Latham 1802)	R	I
8. ORDER - CUCULIFORMES					
24.	Cuculidae	Indian Cuckoo	<i>Cuculus micropterus</i> (Gould, 1837)	R	O
25.		Asian Koel	<i>Eudynamys scolopaceus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	R	O
26.		Greater Coucal	<i>Centropus sinensis</i> (Stephens, 1815)	R	O
9. ORDER - GALLIFORMES					
27.	Phasianidae	Grey Francolin	<i>Francolinus pondicerianus</i> (Gmelin, 1789)	R	O
28.		Black Francolin	<i>Francolinus francolinus</i> (Linnaeus, 1766)	R	O
29.		Rock Bush Quail	<i>Perdica argoondah</i> (Sykes, 1832)	R	O
30.		Jungle Bush Quail	<i>Perdica asiatica</i> (Latham, 1790)	R	O
31.		Indian Peafowl	<i>Pavo cristatus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	R	O

10. ORDER - GRUIFORMES					
32.	Rallidae	Eurasian Moorhen	<i>Gallinula chloropus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	R	O
33.		Eurasian Coot	<i>Fulica atra</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	R	O
34.		White-breasted Waterhen	<i>Amaurornis phoenicurus</i> (Pennant, 1769)	R	O
11. ORDER - PASSERIFORMES					
35.	Alaudidae	Indian Bushlark	<i>Mirafra erythroptera</i> Blyth, 1845	R	O
36.	Aegithinidae	Common Iora	<i>Aegithina tiphia</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	R	I
37.	Campephagide	Large Cuckooshrike	<i>Coracina macei</i> (Lesson, 1830)	R	O
38.	Cisticolidae	Ashy Prinia	<i>Prinia socialis</i> (Sykes, 1832)	R	I
39.		Rufous-fronted Prinia	<i>Prinia buchanani</i> (Blyth, 1844)	R	I
40.		Plain Prinia	<i>Prinia inornata</i> (Sykes, 1832)	R	I
41.		Grey Breasted Prinia	<i>Prinia hodgsonii</i> (Blyth, 1844)	R	I
42.		Common Tailorbird	<i>Orthotomus sutorius</i> (Pennant, 1769)	R	I
43.	Corvidae	House Crow	<i>Corvus splendens</i> (Vieillot, 1817)	R	O
44.		Rufous Treepie	<i>Dendrocitta vagabunda</i> (Latham, 1790)	R	O
45.	Dicuridae	Black Drongo	<i>Dicrurus macrocercus</i> (Vieillot, 1817)	R	O
46.		White-bellied Drongo	<i>Dicrurus caeruleus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	R	O
47.	Emberizidae	Crested Bunting	<i>Emberiza lathami</i> (Gray, 1831)	R	O
48.	Estrildidae	Indian Silver bill	<i>Euodice malabarica</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	R	O
49.	Hirundinidae	Red-rumped Swallow	<i>Cecropis daurica</i> (Linnaeus, 1771)	R	I
50.		Wire-tailed Swallow	<i>Hirundo smithii</i> (Leach, 1818)	R	I
51.	Laniidae	Bay-backed Shrike	<i>Lanius vittatus</i> (Valenciennes, 1826)	R	I
52.		Great grey shrike	<i>Lanius excubitor</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	R	I
53.		Long-tailed Shrike	<i>Lanius schach</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	R	I
54.	Leiotrichidae	Common Babbler	<i>Argya caudata</i> (Dumont, 1823)	R	I & G
55.		Large Gray Babbler	<i>Argya malcolmi</i> (Sykes, 1832)	R	I & G
56.		Jungle Babbler	<i>Turdoides striata</i> (Dumont, 1823)	R	I & G
57.	Motacillidae	White Wagtail	<i>Motacilla alba</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	WV	IO
58.		Yellow Wagtail	<i>Motacilla flava</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	WV	IO
59.		White-browed Wagtail	<i>Motacilla maderaspatensis</i> (Gmelin, 1789)	R	IO
60.	Muscicapidae	Siberian Stone chat	<i>Saxicola maurus</i> (Pallas, 1773)	WV	I
61.		Pied Bush chat	<i>Saxicola caprata</i> (Linnaeus, 1766)	WV	I
62.		Indian Robin	<i>Copsychus fulicatus</i> (Linnaeus, 1766)	R	I
63.		Oriental Magpie Robin	<i>Copsychus saularis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	R	O
64.		Black Redstart	<i>Phoenicurus ochruros</i> (Gmelin, 1774)	WV	O
65.		Red-breasted Flycatcher	<i>Ficedula parva</i> (Bechstein, 1792)	WV	I
66.	Nectariniidae	Purple Sunbird	<i>Cinnyris asiaticus</i> (Latham, 1790)	R	N
67.	Oriolidae	Indian Golden Oriole	<i>Oriolus kundoo</i> (Sykes, 1832)	SV	O
68.	Paridae	Cinereous Tit	<i>Parus cinereus</i> (Vieillot, 1818)	R	I
69.	Passeridae	House Sparrow	<i>Passer domesticus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	R	O
70.		Yellow Throated Sparrow	<i>Gymnoris xanthocollis</i> (Burton, 1838)	R	O
71.	Ploceidae	Baya Weaver	<i>Ploceus philippinus</i> (Linnaeus, 1766)	R	O
72.	Phylloscopidae	Common Chiffchaff	<i>Phylloscopus collybita</i> (Vieillot, 1817)	WV	I
73.	Pycnonotidae	Red-vented Bulbul	<i>Pycnonotus cafer</i> (Linnaeus, 1766)	R	O
74.		White-eared Bulbul	<i>Pycnonotus leucotis</i> (Gould, 1836)	R	O
75.	Rhipiduridae	White-browed Fantail	<i>Rhipidura aureola</i> (Lesson, 1830)	R	I

76.	Stenostiridae	Grey-headed Canary-flycatcher	<i>Culicicapa ceylonensis</i> (Swainson, 1820)	R	I
77.	Sturnidae	Asian Pied Starling	<i>Gracupica contra</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	R	O
78.		Brahminy Starling	<i>Sturnia pagodarum</i> (Gmelin, 1789)	R	O
79.		Rosy Starling	<i>Pastor roseus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	WV	O
80.		Bank Myna	<i>Acridotheres ginginianus</i> (Latham, 1790)	R	O
81.		Common Myna	<i>Acridotheres tristis</i> (Linnaeus, 1766)	R	O
82.	Paradoxornithidae	Yellow-eyed Babbler	<i>Chrysomma sinense</i> (Gmelin, 1789)	R	O
83.	Sylviidae	Lesser Whitethroat	<i>Sylvia curruca</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	WV	O
84.	Vangidae	Common Wood shrike	<i>Tephrodornis pondicerianus</i> (Gmelin, 1789)	R	I
12. ORDER-ELECANIFORMES					
85.	Ardeidae	Great Egret	<i>Ardea alba</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	R	C
86.		Intermediate Egret	<i>Ardea intermedia</i> (Wagler, 1827)	R	C
87.		Eastern Cattle Egret	<i>Bubulcus coromandus</i> (Boddaert, 1783)	R	C
88.		Indian Pond heron	<i>Ardeola grayii</i> (Sykes, 1832)	R	C
13. ORDER - PICIFORMES					
89.	Megalaimidae	Coppersmith Barbet	<i>Psilopogon haemacephalus</i> (Müller, 1776)	R	F & I
90.	Picidae	Black-Rumped Flame-back/ Lessar Flameback Woodpecker	<i>Dinopium benghalense</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	R	O
91.		Yellow-crowned woodpecker	<i>Leiopicus mahrattensis</i> (Latham, 1801)	R	I
14. ORDER – PODICIPEDIFORMES					
92.	Podicipedidae	Little Grebe	<i>Tachybaptus ruficollis</i> (Pallas, 1764)	R	C
15. ORDER - PSITTACIFORMES					
93.	Psittacidae	Rose Ringed Parakeet	<i>Psittacula krameri</i> (Scopoli, 1769)	R	F & G
94.		Plum-headed Parakeet	<i>Psittacula cyanocephala</i> (Linnaeus, 1766)	R	F & G
16. ORDER - STRIGIFORMES					
95.	Strigidae	Spotted Owlet	<i>Athene brama</i> (Temminck, 1821)	R	C
96.		Indian Scops Owl	<i>Otus bakkamoena</i> (Pennant, 1769)	R	C

Feeding Guild: O= Omnivore, C= Carnivore, I= Insectivore, F= Frugivore, N= Nectarivore, G=Granivore, F= Frugivore.

Migratory Status- R= Resident, WV= Winter visitor, SV= Summer Visitor, LM =Local migrant

1. *Accipiter badius* (Gmelin, 1788)

2. *Circaetus gallicus* (Gmelin, 1788)

3. *Elanus caeruleus* (Desfontaines, 1789)

4. *Sarkidiornis melanotos* (Pennant, 1769)

5. *Apus affinis* (Gray, 1830)

6. *Upupa epops* Linnaeus, 1758

7. *Ocyrceros birostris* (Scopoli, 1786)

8. *Vanellus malabaricus* (Boddaert, 1783)

9. *Vanellus indicus* (Boddaert, 1783)

10. *Himantopus himantopus* (Linnaeus, 1758)

11. *Tringa glareola* Linnaeus, 1758

12. *Actitis hypoleucos* (Linnaeus, 1758)

13. *Tringa ochropus* Linnaeus, 1758

14. *Turnix suscitator* (Gmelin, 1789)

15. *Spilopelia senegalensis* (Linnaeus, 1766)

16. *Streptopelia tranquebarica* (Hermann, 1804)

17. *Streptopelia decaocto* Frivaldszky, 1838

18. *Treron phoenicopterus* (Latham, 1790)

19. *Columba livia* (Gmelin, 1789)

20. *Halcyon smyrnensis* (Linnaeus, 1758)

21. *Coracias benghalensis* (Linnaeus, 1758)

22. *Merops persicus* Pallas, 1773

23. *Merops orientalis* Latham 1802

24. *Cuculus micropterus* Gould, 1837

25. *Eudynamys scolopaceus* (Linnaeus, 1758)

26. *Centropus sinensis* Stresemann, 1913

27. *Francolinus pondicerianus* (Gmelin, 1789)

28. *Francolinus francolinus* (Linnaeus, 1766)

29. *Perdica argoondah* (Sykes, 1832)

30. *Perdica asiatica* (Latham, 1790)

31. *Pavo cristatus* (Linnaeus, 1758)

32. *Gallinula chloropus* ((Linnaeus, 1758)

33. *Fulica atra* Linnaeus, 1758

34. *Amauornis phoenicurus* (Pennant, 1769)

35. *Mirafra erythroptera* Blyth, 1845

36. *Aegithina tiphia* (Linnaeus, 1758)

37. *Coracina macei* (Lesson, 1830)

38. *Prinia socialis* Sykes, 1832

39. *Prinia buchanani* Blyth, 1844

40. *Prinia inornata* Sykes, 1832

41. *Prinia hodgsonii* Blyth, 1844

42. *Orthotomus sutorius* (Pennant, 1769)

43. *Corvus splendens* Vieillot, 1817

44. *Dendrocitta vagabunda* (Latham, 1790)

45. *Dicrurus macrocercus* Vieillot, 1817

46. *Dicrurus caerulescens* (Linnaeus, 1758)

47. *Emberiza lathamii* Gray, 1831

48. *Euodice malabarica* (Linnaeus, 1758)

49. *Cecropis daurica* Linnaeus, 1771

50. *Hirundo smithii* Leach, 1818

51. *Lanius vittatus* Valenciennes, 1826

52. *Lanius excubiter* (Linnaeus, 1758)

53. *Lanius schach* (Linnaeus, 1758)

54. *Argya caudate* (Dumont, 1823)

55. *Argya malcolmi* (Sykes, 1832)

56. *Turdoides striata* (Dumont, 1823)

57. *Motacilla alba* Linnaeus, 1758

58. *Motacilla flava* Linnaeus, 1758

59. *Motacilla maderaspatensis* Gmelin, 1789

60. *Saxicola maurus* (Linnaeus, 1766)

61. *Saxicola maurus* (Pallas, 1773)

62. *Saxicola idesfulvicatus* (Linnaeus, 1766)

63. *Copsychus saularis* (Linnaeus, 1758)

64. *Phoenicurus ochruros* (Gmelin, 1774)

65. *Ficedula parva* (Bechstein, 1792)

66. *Cinnyris asiaticus* (Latham, 1790)

67. *Oriolus kundoo* Sykes, 1832

68. *Parus cinereus* Linnaeus, 1758

69. *Passer domesticus* (Linnaeus, 1758)

70. *Gymnoris xanthocollis* (Burton, 1838)

71. *Ploceus philippinus* (Linnaeus, 1766)

72. *Phylloscopus collybita* (Vieillot, 1817)

73. *Pycnonotus cafer* (Linnaeus, 1766)

74. *Pycnonotus leucotis* (Gould, 1836)

75. *Rhipidura aureola* Lesson, 1830

76. *Culicicapa ceylonensis* (Swainson, 1820)

77. *Gracupica contra* (Linnaeus, 1758)

78. *Sturnia pagodarum* (Gmelin, 1789)

79. *Pastor roseus* (Linnaeus, 1758)

80. *Acridotheres ginginianus* (Latham, 1790)

81. *Acridotheres tristis* (Linnaeus, 1766)

82. *Chrysomma sinense* (Gmelin, 1789)

83. *Sylvia curruca* (Linnaeus, 1758)

84. *Tephrodornis pondicerianus* (Gmelin, 1789)

85. *Ardea alba* Linnaeus, 1758

86. *Ardea intermedia* Wagler, 1827

87. *Bubulcus coromandus* (Boddaert, 1783)

88. *Ardeola grayii* (Sykes, 1832)

89. *Psilopogon haemacephalus* (Müller, 1776)

90. *Dinopium benghalense* (Linnaeus, 1758)

91. *Leiopicus mahrattensis* (Latham, 1801)

92. *Tachybaptus ruficollis* (Pallas, 1764)

93. *Psittacula krameri* (Scopoli, 1769)

94. *Psittacula cyanocephala* (Linnaeus, 1766)

95. *Athene brama* (Temminck, 1821)

96. *Otus bakkamoena* Pennant, 1769